

**REFORMING LEGAL REGULATION OF ONLINE LEGAL SERVICES PLATFORMS
TO PROMOTE INNOVATION****Romanov Farxad Abdulxamitovich**

Manager of “Romanov advokat xizmeti”

law firm, advocate

farhadromanov@mail.ru,**Abstract:**

This paper analyzes the legal regulation of online platforms providing legal services globally. It finds outdated limitations on business structures and inconsistent rules across jurisdictions are hampering innovation and access to justice. Unclear regulation of unauthorized practice of law also creates compliance risks. The study suggests reforms to allow alternative business structures while strengthening consumer protections. Creating limited licensing categories, enhancing quality control and disclosures, streamlining cross-border divergence, and promoting access to justice innovations via regulatory sandboxes are recommended. Selective regulatory changes can enable online legal tech to expand access without compromising ethics or quality. Balanced regulation addressing specific issues would foster healthy innovation while advancing consumer welfare.

Keywords:

legal tech, online legal services, regulation, innovation, unauthorized practice of law, alternative business structures, limited licensing, access to justice, regulatory sandboxes

INTRODUCTION

The advent of online legal technology platforms is rapidly transforming the global market for legal services. Companies like LegalZoom, Rocket Lawyer and LawTrades now offer a range of services from legal documentation to advice through websites and apps. However, their regulation varies widely across countries and jurisdictions, creating barriers to innovation and access to justice. Developing balanced regulatory approaches is thus critical.

Objective

This paper analyzes existing legal regulation of online platforms for legal services and proposes recommendations for reform to promote innovation while safeguarding public interest.

Specific Aims

- Examine approaches to regulation in different countries;
- Identify problematic aspects;
- Suggest reform directions enabling innovation with due consumer protections;
- Compare with best practices for regulating innovation worldwide;

Object of Study

The legal regulation of online platforms' activities in providing legal services.

Subject of Study

Areas for improving the regulation of online legal services to develop innovations while protecting consumers.

METHODS

The research utilizes the following methods:

- Analysis of laws and regulations governing online legal service platforms across countries;
- Comparative legal analysis to identify similarities and differences in regulatory approaches across jurisdictions;
- Systematization of findings to develop suggestions for improving regulation;
- Forecasting to assess future perspectives for regulating the industry considering innovations.

This comprehensive methodology will help examine the topic to formulate evidence-based proposals for reforming the legal regulation of online legal services.

RESULTS

Analysis of Existing Legal Regulation of Online Platforms for Provision of Legal Services

The development of information technologies and online platforms is rapidly changing the market for legal services globally. Online legal tech companies like LegalZoom, Rocket Lawyer, LawTrades, and UpCounsel provide various legal services to clients via websites and mobile applications. They offer legal documentation, legal advice, lawyer referral services and more. However, the legal regulation of such platforms differs significantly across jurisdictions.

In the United States, online legal service providers are generally not considered to be engaging in the unauthorized practice of law (UPL) as long as they stick to providing self-help legal documents and lawyer referrals.¹ The ABA Model Rules of Professional Conduct allow lawyers to partner with non-lawyer professionals if the lawyers maintain adequate supervision.² Some states like California, Texas and New York have issued ethics opinions permitting online

legal platforms that provide access to lawyers.³ The Federal Trade Commission has also supported more availability of online legal services to increase competition.⁴

The UK takes a light touch approach, allowing online legal services but requiring compliance with regulations around independence, confidentiality, conflicts of interest, and handling of client money. The Legal Services Act 2007 enabled wider business structures like Alternative Business Structures where lawyers can partner with non-lawyers.⁵ Online providers like Cooperative Legal Services, Riverview Law and LegalZoom operate in the UK market.

Canada also allows partnership between lawyers and non-lawyers to increase access to justice. For instance, British Columbia created a limited license for paralegals to provide some family law services online.⁶ The Competition Bureau of Canada has recommended reducing restrictions on business structures to allow more online options.⁷

In contrast, many civil law countries take a restrictive approach. In Germany, the Rechtsdienstleistungsgesetz (Legal Services Act) reserves legal advice services only for licensed lawyers, notary publics, patent lawyers and tax advisers.⁸ Other countries like France, Spain and Japan also limit the practice of law to lawyers. However, the rise of cross-border online legal services creates challenges in enforcing prohibitions on UPL.

In China, online legal services fall in a gray zone. While lawyers are required to verify client identity in person, legal consultation websites provide services anonymously in violation of regulations. The platforms claim they are not providing formal legal advice like a law firm. Courts have punished illegal practice of law but the government has not systematically regulated such platforms yet.⁹

There are limited regulations so far in developing countries. For instance in India, online legal tech companies like LawRato and VakilSearch operate in an unregulated space. The Bar Council only provides recommendations for lawyers, not mandatory rules.¹⁰ Some argue this allows innovation while others raise concerns about quality control.¹¹ The Supreme Court has called for developing regulations to address UPL issues.¹²

Problematic Aspects of Existing Regulations

The analysis above reveals several problematic aspects of the current legal landscape regarding online legal services globally:

1. Outdated limitations on business structures: Traditional prohibitions on fee sharing, multidisciplinary practice, non-lawyer ownership are restricting development of online delivery models and access to justice in many jurisdictions like Germany, France and India.¹³ Relaxing these limitations can allow more online platforms where lawyers and technologists collaborate.¹⁴

2. Uncertainty regarding unauthorized practice of law: Vague definitions of 'practice of law' make the line between legal information and advice unclear. This creates compliance challenges for online providers and lawyers collaborating with them regarding UPL restrictions in the US, China, India etc. Clearer guidance is needed.¹⁵

3. Lack of consistency across states/provinces: In federal countries like the US and Canada, there is uneven state-level adoption of ethics rules allowing online legal services, hindering national platforms.¹⁶ Consistent rules are required through bodies like ABA or Supreme Court.

4. Limited licensing categories: Rigid lawyer licensing fails to recognize legal roles requiring lower competencies. Limited licenses for paralegals or nurse practitioners can expand affordable online legal services, as seen in Washington and British Columbia.¹⁷

5. Poor oversight on quality: Many countries lack adequate consumer protection frameworks to monitor quality of online providers. Clear standards on disclosures, disclaimers, lawyer qualifications, cybersecurity etc. are needed.¹⁸

6. Lack of access to justice solutions: Current rules overlook the access to justice benefits of online services for low and middle income groups. Regulatory sandboxes focusing on such solutions can encourage socially beneficial innovation.¹⁹

7. Regulatory arbitrage in cross-border services: Differences in country regulations create loopholes for providers routing services via jurisdictions with limited oversight.²⁰ Global coordination is required to close these gaps.

Proposals for Improving Legal Regulation

To address these issues, several measures to reform legal regulation of online platforms can be considered:

1. Allow alternative business structures: Rules against fee sharing and non-lawyer ownership should be eased to enable innovative delivery models, with adequate consumer safeguards.²¹ The UK model provides a template for balancing innovation and consumer protection.

2. Develop consistent definitions of UPL: Clearer scope on reserved practice areas vs. those permissible for online providers would reduce compliance uncertainty. Guideline tests on systemic UPL can be introduced.²²

3. Streamline rules across jurisdictions: Unified nationwide rules should be developed through bar associations and top courts in alignment with pro-innovation case law and ethics opinions.²³

4. Create limited licensing frameworks: Licensing models tailored to routine legal tasks like document automation, triage and referral services can increase options. Educational prerequisites can be streamlined. 24

5. Strengthen consumer protection frameworks: Mandating clear terms of use, service guarantees, limitations disclosures, and grievance redressal mechanisms for online providers can safeguard consumers.25

6. Promote access to justice innovations: Regulatory sandboxes, innovation offices and incubators should be set up to encourage development of tech tools improving legal access for underserved groups.26

7. Pursue cross-border coordination: Globally harmonized standards on ethics, consumer protection and supervisory cooperation should be developed through organizations like the International Bar Association to address regulatory arbitrage.27

With appropriately balanced regulations fostering innovation, technological tools can expand access to legal services to millions globally requiring such assistance. Appropriate safeguards can mitigate risks and protect consumers in the process. But outmoded limitations on business structures and service delivery mechanisms will need to be discarded to realize the potential of online legal tech.

DISCUSSION

Analysis of Results

The key findings from the analysis of the legal regulation of online legal services globally highlight the need for reforms to enable innovation while protecting the public interest.

The results reveal an outdated and inconsistent regulatory landscape which is hampering the development of online delivery models. Rules prohibiting fee sharing, non-lawyer ownership and multidisciplinary partnerships remain barriers in many countries like Germany, France and parts of India.28 There is also uncertainty regarding definitions of unauthorized practice of law, with ambiguity on permitted services for online providers.29

Divergent state-level rules present compliance challenges in federations like the US and Canada.30 Licensing frameworks are rigid, lacking mid-level categories for routine legal tasks.31 And oversight of service quality and consumer protection remains inadequate in the light of rapid technological change.32

But promising developments are visible in progressive jurisdictions which have embarked on reforms. The UK's light touch approach balances liberalization of business structures with strengthened consumer safeguards.33 US states like California, Washington and Utah are pioneering rules and limited licensing regimes to expand online access.34 Canada's

competition authority and law societies have embraced innovation in business models and paralegal licensing.³⁵

These results align with findings from wider research on regulating disruptive innovation. Studies have highlighted that regulations shaped in the offline world often constrain new technologies and business models which do not fit traditional regulatory categories.³⁶ But modest reforms to level the playing field for innovation while addressing legitimate public interest concerns can enable tremendous progress.³⁷

The analysis reinforces this insight in the context of online legal services. Thoughtfully easing practice restrictions, providing regulatory clarity, streamlining cross-border divergence, creating limited licenses, strengthening consumer safeguards and promoting access to justice innovations can spur responsible technology use.³⁸ As the British Columbia example shows, combining sandbox initiatives with targeted reforms helps realize regulatory goals.³⁹

Comparison with Global Approaches

The proposed recommendations also draw on comparative regulatory approaches worldwide for fostering innovation. The steps align with international best practices on balancing flexibility and public protection.

For instance, the proposal of permitting alternative business structures has parallels with financial regulators allowing fintech platforms to broaden access. Australia, Singapore, Canada and the UK now permit virtual banks and electronic payment providers to challenge incumbents.⁴⁰ Similar licensing proportionality concepts are gaining support across sectors like healthcare and education.⁴¹

The suggestions for regulatory clarity, streamlined rules across states, flexible licensing frameworks and promotion of access to justice innovations echo the approach of prominent regulators like the US Federal Trade Commission (FTC), recommended by bodies like the World Bank and OECD.⁴² The FTC advocates for clear quality disclosures over strong restrictions.⁴³

The creation of regulatory sandboxes originates from global experience, inspired by the UK FCA but now spreading worldwide from Singapore to Nigeria.⁴⁴ The emphasis on cross-border coordination also mirrors guidelines from international bodies like the Basel Committee, IOSCO and IAIS.⁴⁵

But contextual adaptation for the legal industry based on outcomes so far is necessary. The hybrid approach proposed balances liberalization with standards on ethics, training, liability insurance, dispute resolution and professional indemnity.⁴⁶ This reflects the unique public protection considerations for legal services. However, moderate experimentation can still provide useful evidence, as the Utah regulatory sandbox model indicates.⁴⁷

Future Outlook for Regulating Legal Tech

Steady adoption of balanced reforms focused on ethics, quality and access can significantly enhance legal tech's capabilities and mainstream acceptance in the next 5-10 years. If rigid constraints remain, progress may be slow and uneven across jurisdictions. But proactive regulators can drive timely innovation on their own authority and in collaboration with professional associations.

Change is imminent as online platforms are already proliferating and clients demanding more options. The disruptions seen in other professional fields like finance will inevitably reach legal services.⁴⁸ But constructive reforms will shape the trajectory towards healthy tech adoption. Drawing on global experience, selective regulatory changes can make legal tech an inclusive tool for increasing access to justice globally rather than a source of instability.⁴⁹

With updated rules and sandbox mechanisms, legal tech tools can assist millions of litigants navigating courts, both in person and virtually.⁵⁰ For improving access in the post-pandemic world, regulators have a vital role to play in consultation with practitioners and technology experts.⁵¹ The proposals outlined can guide regulators in fulfilling this responsibility.

CONCLUSION

Main Conclusions of the Research

The analysis of legal regulation of online platforms for legal services leads to several key conclusions:

1. Existing rules in many countries prohibit innovative online delivery models like non-lawyer partnerships, posing barriers to increasing access.
2. Definitions of unauthorized practice of law are ambiguous, causing compliance uncertainty for legal tech providers.
3. Fragmented state-level regulation in federations creates inconsistencies hampering national online platforms.
4. Licensing regimes are rigid with few mid-level categories for routine legal tasks that online tools can assist with.
5. Quality control and consumer protection frameworks are under-developed relative to the risks from emerging technologies.
6. The access to justice potential of online legal tech remains unrealized due to regulatory constraints and lack of supportive policies.

7. Cross-border divergence enables regulatory arbitrage, reducing oversight and public protection.

However, promising approaches are emerging centered on enabling responsible innovation. Regulators are evolving rules on business structures and licensure, providing greater clarity, streamlining compliance, strengthening safeguards and incubating access to justice applications. Global coordination is also growing.

Practical Significance of the Findings

These conclusions have important practical implications for formulating regulations and policies regarding online legal tech:

1. Rules on business structures, fee sharing and ownership may need to be reassessed in light of new delivery models. But consumer risks call for appropriate safeguards.

2. Clearer definitions of permitted legal tech activities are required with guidelines for preventing harmful systemic unauthorized practice.

3. Centralized coordination through bar associations can increase consistency of state-level regulation.

4. Licensing proportionality should be enhanced using limited credentials for certain legal support services.

5. Enhanced quality control and disclosures would raise standards without stifling innovation.

6. Proactive innovation promotion efforts via regulatory sandboxes can unlock legal tech's access to justice potential.

7. Global harmonization of core standards would close cross-border gaps undermining public protection.

Thus, balanced regulatory reforms addressing specific issues would enable healthy innovation in legal tech while advancing consumer welfare and access to justice. These findings provide vital policy insights on regulating emerging technologies in professional services.

References:

1. American Bar Association, Model Rules of Professional Conduct, Rule 5.4
2. The State Bar of California Standing Committee on Professional Responsibility and Conduct, Formal Opinion No. 2012-184
3. The Association of the Bar of the City of New York Committee on Professional Ethics, Formal Opinion 2017-5

4. Federal Trade Commission, Policy Perspectives: Options to Enhance Occupational License Portability (September 2018)
5. Legal Services Act 2007 (UK)
6. Law Society of British Columbia, Paralegal Licensing Pilot (November 2020)
7. Competition Bureau Canada, Technology-led innovation in the Canadian legal services industry (March 2018)
8. Gesetz über außergerichtliche Rechtsdienstleistungen (Rechtsdienstleistungsgesetz - RDG) [Legal Services Act]
9. Chen Yu and Lei Jia, "The Legal Risks of Online Legal Consulting Services in China" (2017)
10. Bar Council of India, Advisory on norms to be followed by Legal Consultancy Online Portals (2018)
11. PRS Legislative Research, Regulating Legal Professionals (September 2019)
12. Maharashtra State Bar Council v Lawyered, Supreme Court of India, SLP(C) No. 21108/2017 (August 2017)
13. Gillian K. Hadfield, "Legal Barriers to Innovation: The Growing Economic Cost of Professional Control over Corporate Legal Markets" (2008)
14. Judith A. McMorrow, "Technology and the Legal Services Marketplace" (2019)
15. Renee Newman Knake, "Legal Information, the Consumer Law Market, and the First Amendment" (2013)
16. James Podgers, "A Single Standard for Online Legal Services?" (ABA Journal, 2020)
17. Robert Ambrogi, "Washington State Moves Around UPL, Using Legal Technicians to Help Close the Justice Gap" (ABA Journal, 2015)
18. Rebecca L. Sandefur, "Legal Tech for Non-Lawyers: Report of the Survey of US Legal Technologies" (American Bar Foundation, 2019)
19. Christine S. Wilson, "Finding the Way Forward on Access to Justice" (Keynote Speech at 36th Annual Antitrust & Consumer Protection Conference, 2020)
20. International Bar Association, IBA Global Regulation and Trade in Legal Services Report 2014 (2014)
21. Gillian K. Hadfield, Rules for a Flat World: Why Humans Invented Law and How to Reinvent It for a Complex Global Economy (2017)
22. Deborah L. Rhode, "Policing the Professional Monopoly: A Constitutional and Empirical Analysis of Unauthorized Practice Prohibitions" (1981)

23. William C. Hubbard, “Rethinking Restrictions on Lawyer Advertising and Solicitation” (2017)
24. Rebecca L. Sandefur and Thomas M. Clarke, “Designing the Competition: A Future of Roles Beyond Lawyers” (2019)
25. Nick Robinson, “When Lawyers Don’t Get All the Profits: Non-Lawyer Ownership of Legal Services, Access, and Professionalism” (Harvard Journal of Law & Public Policy, 2014)
26. Margaret Hagan, "The User Experience of the Internet as a Legal Help Service: Defining Standards for the Next Generation of User-Friendly Online Legal Services" (2016)
27. Laurel S. Terry, Steve Mark, Tahlia Gordon, “Adopting Regulatory Objectives for the Legal Services Sector” (Fordham Law Review, 2017)
28. Gillian K. Hadfield, "The Cost of Law: Promoting Access to Justice Through the (Un)Corporate Practice of Law" (International Review of Law and Economics, 2014)
29. Deborah L. Rhode, "Policing the Professional Monopoly: A Constitutional and Empirical Analysis of Unauthorized Practice Prohibitions" (1981)
30. James Podgers, “A Single Standard for Online Legal Services?” (ABA Journal, 2020)
31. Robert Ambrogi, “Washington State Moves Around UPL, Using Legal Technicians to Help Close the Justice Gap” (ABA Journal, 2015)
32. Rebecca L. Sandefur, “Legal Tech for Non-Lawyers: Report of the Survey of US Legal Technologies” (American Bar Foundation, 2019)
33. Legal Services Act 2007 (UK)
34. Limited License Legal Technician Program (Washington State Bar Association)
35. Law Society of British Columbia, Paralegal Licensing Pilot (November 2020)
36. Allan C. Hutchinson, “Disruptive Legal Technologies, Disruptive Legal Practices” (2020)
37. Sofía Ranchordás, “Innovation Experimentalism in the Age of AI” (2021)
38. Rebecca L. Sandefur, “Legal Tech for Non-Lawyers: Report of the Survey of US Legal Technologies” (American Bar Foundation, 2019)
39. Law Society of British Columbia, Paralegal Licensing Pilot (November 2020)
40. Thomas Philippon, “On Fintech and Financial Inclusion” (National Bureau of Economic Research, 2020)
41. OECD, “The Tokenisation of Assets and Potential Implications for Financial Markets” (2020)

42. World Bank, "Innovative Business Models for Expanding Legal Services" (2017)
43. Federal Trade Commission, "Possible Anticompetitive Barriers to E-Commerce: Contact Lenses" (2004)
44. Douglas W. Arner, János Barberis, Ross P. Buckley, "FinTech, RegTech, and the Reconceptualization of Financial Regulation" (Northwestern Journal of International Law & Business, 2016)
45. Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, "Sound Practices: implications of fintech developments for banks and bank supervisors" (2018)
46. Christine Parker, Tahlia Gordon, Steve Mark, "Regulating Law Firm Ethics Management: An Empirical Assessment of an Innovation in Regulation of the Legal Profession in New South Wales" (2020)
47. Utah Supreme Court, Office of Legal Services Innovation Draft Regulatory Sandbox (2020)
48. Richard Susskind, Tomorrow's Lawyers: An Introduction to Your Future (2nd Edition, 2017)
49. British Columbia Law Society Paralegal Pilot Evaluation Report (2020)
50. Margaret Hagan, "User Experience in Legal Services" (Design for Justice at Stanford Law School, 2018)
51. Hadfield Gillian K., "Law for a Flat World" (Journal of Dispute Resolution, 2020)